

Correlation between Transcutaneous and Serum Bilirubin in Preterm Neonates Before, During and Post Phototherapy: A Prospective Observational Study

Rakesh Bairwa¹, Nishant Aswani², Prabhudev Basavaraj Hasbi³, Jitendra Kumar Jain⁴, Gopi Kishan Sharma⁵, Amrit Lal Bairwa⁶

¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Sawai Man Singh Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, American International Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, KLE Jagadguru Gangadhar Mahaswamigalu Mooruvavirmath Medical College (KLE JGMMMC), Hubballi, Karnataka, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Government Medical College, Kota, Rajasthan, India

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Government Medical College, Kota, Rajasthan, India

⁶Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Government Medical College, Kota, Rajasthan, India

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Corresponding author: Dr Jitendra Kumar Jain

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Abstract

Introduction: Hyperbilirubinemia is the single most common abnormal physical finding in majority of preterm neonates. Phototherapy plays a significant role in the treatment and prevention of hyperbilirubinemia in neonates. Transcutaneous measurement of bilirubin concentration is considered to be ideal for screening of neonatal jaundice as they are immediate and can indicate the need for total serum bilirubin testing. Reduction in number of invasive blood tests is associated with reduction in pain and discomfort for newborns and in parental distress and reduction in health costs.

Aims and Objective: To study correlation between Transcutaneous Bilirubin (TcB) with Total Serum Bilirubin (TSB) in preterm neonates before, during and post phototherapy.

Methods: This is a prospective observational study conducted in department of Pediatrics, J. K. Lon Mother and Child Hospital, attached to Government Medical College, Kota. 190 preterm neonates (28 to 37 weeks) requiring phototherapy for the first time were enrolled in this study. TcB and TSB was assessed pre-, during and 24 hours post-phototherapy over mid sternum. The area of 2.5cm diameter on mid sternum where TcB was assessed was patched with photo-opaque material before starting of phototherapy. The decision to initiate and stop phototherapy was as per the NICE guideline recommendations.

Results: It was found that TSB and TcB has good correlation before phototherapy ($r=0.97$). The total serum bilirubin decreases significantly after phototherapy.

Conclusion: Transcutaneous bilirubin correlates significantly with total serum bilirubin at the patched sternal site before phototherapy in preterm neonates.

Keywords: Phototherapy, Transcutaneous Bilirubinometry, Hyperbilirubinemia, Jaundice, Preterm.

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Introduction

Hyperbilirubinemia is a common & benign problem observed during the 1st week after birth in approximately 60% of term infants and 80% of preterm infants. [1] The yellow colour usually results from the accumulation of unconjugated, nonpolar, lipid-soluble bilirubin pigment in the skin which is an end product of heme metabolism. [1] Physiological jaundice may provide useful protection to the baby against oxygen free radical triggered neonatal disorders because bilirubin is a potent antioxidant. [4]

The potential toxicity of bilirubin in form of acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus are associated with significant mortality and morbidity in neonatal age group. [2] Preterm neonates are susceptible to higher risk of kernicterus at low bilirubin values due to a slower postnatal maturation of hepatic bilirubin uptake and conjugation mechanisms. In addition, delay in establishing enteral feeding in preterm infants contributes further to severe jaundice in this population therefore early prevention, diagnosis and interventions require. [5]

Phototherapy acts as a drug & plays a significant role in the treatment and prevention of hyperbilirubinemia in neonates. This relatively common therapy lowers the serum bilirubin level by photo-oxidation of bilirubin into water-soluble isomers that can be eliminated without conjugation in the liver. [4]

The effectiveness of phototherapy depends upon the type of light source used (i.e., dose, spectral emission curve, depth of penetration), the distance between the light and the infant, the surface area treated, the aetiology of the jaundice and total serum bilirubin level at the onset of phototherapy. [2, 5]

Total serum bilirubin [TSB] level assessment in clinical laboratory is an

objective method, but the results provided are not real-time. It is expensive, and there is significant inter- and intra-laboratory variability. The necessary blood sampling is painful and associated with the possibility of local infection. [2]

Transcutaneous measurement of bilirubin concentration is considered to be ideal for neonatal jaundice screening. Transcutaneous readings are immediate, and they can indicate the need for total serum bilirubin testing. Reduction in number of invasive blood tests is associated with reduction in pain and discomfort for newborns and in parental distress and reduction in health costs. [2]

Material and Methods

Place of study: This is a prospective observational study conducted over a one-year duration in NICU of department of Pediatrics, Government Medical College & associated group of hospitals Kota from December 2019 to January 2020. All preterm newborn babies admitted with history of neonatal jaundice requiring phototherapy for the first time were selected.

The inclusion criteria: Were preterm neonates with gestational age at birth >28 weeks and <37 weeks with jaundice and parents who were willing to participate in the study.

The exclusion criteria: Were not willing for participation, those previously treated with phototherapy prior to enrolment, jaundice requiring exchange transfusion, generalised skin disease, history of birth asphyxia, major congenital malformation, sepsis, necrotising enterocolitis, suspected or confirmed hepatic disease, preterm suffering from other serious illness during or prior to study, neonates with gestational age <28 weeks and 37 weeks.

Written informed consent was obtained from either of parents or guardians prior to

enrolment in the study. Ethical clearance was obtained by letter number 1804 dated on 16/12/2019, from Institutional Ethics Committee on human subject research

before the commencement of the study. The primary aim of the study was to correlate between TcB and TSB in preterm neonates before, during and after phototherapy.

The sample size (n) was calculated according to the formula:

$$n = \frac{z^2 p(1-p)}{d^2} \approx 174$$

$z = 1.96$, for a confidence level [α] of 95%,

$p = 0.13$, proportion (expressed as a decimal),

$e = 0.05$, margin of error.

Figure 1: Flow chart of participated neonates

All relevant data was entered into a predesigned proforma. Apart from jaundice their physical examination was completely normal. All investigation needed for the study was conducted free of cost in our hospital under JSSY and BSBY. TSB was estimated using diazo method in machine.

Simultaneously, the TcB was measured on sternum using Dragger jaundice meter-JM103. Out of the three consecutive readings, maximum value of TcB was recorded in mg/dL. The device was calibrated before use, as per manufacturer's recommendations. Phototherapy (compact

fluorescent light or light emitting diode units with an irradiance of 20-30 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2/\text{nm}$) was started, if the TSB fulfilled the criteria as per sliding scale for preterm neonates. Skin over the sternum was shielded from phototherapy light by using opaque headband (Bili band) thus providing TcB readings from the covered site for the comparison with TSB to overcome TcB inaccuracy during phototherapy. The TSB and TcB was recorded within 15 minutes of each other. No additional blood investigations were done for the purpose of this study. First TSB and TcB assessment was done before initiation of phototherapy. Second reading was noted within 24 hours of initiation of phototherapy. Evaluation of neonatal jaundice and management with phototherapy were done as per NICE guidelines.

Measurement of Transcutaneous Bilirubin [TcB]

TcB is a useful adjunct to TSB measurement, and routine employment of TcB can reduce the need for blood sampling

by nearly 30%. Hour specific TcB can be used for prediction of subsequent hyperbilirubinemia. TcB value below 50th centile for age would rule out the risk subsequent hyperbilirubinemia with high probability [high negative predictive value].

The Minolta Jaundice Meter-103 determines the yellowness of the subcutaneous tissue of a new-born infant by measuring the difference between optical densities for light in the blue and green wavelength regions. Since the optical density difference shows a linear correlation with serum bilirubin concentration, it is converted into TSB and indicated digitally.

Advantages of the non-invasive measuring technique are real-time results, cost-effectiveness and avoidance of pain and local infection. Minolta JM-103 TcB assessment demonstrates significant accuracy compared to TSB and can be used as a screening test to identify the need for blood sampling for TSB levels in term and near-term new-born infant. [2]

The Minolta JM-103 probe was placed against the sternum of the infant in a supine position. Highest reading of three consecutive readings over each measurement was displayed as the transcutaneous bilirubin [TcB] level in mg/dl. Blood samples were drawn from a peripheral vein within 10 minutes of transcutaneous measurement. TSB levels were measured in our hospital's clinical chemistry laboratory using the method of diazo method. One transcutaneous measurement and one laboratory measurement were performed in each newborn before, during and after phototherapy. [2,18]

Results

Baseline demographic characteristics of study population included mean gestation age for preterm neonates which was 34.9 weeks, out of which 59% were male neonates, with mean birth weight of 2.11 kg's, mean age of presentation for jaundice

are 4.8 days. Majority of neonates [93.7%] had jaundice on day of life 4th to 7th. Only 4.2% neonates presented with jaundice within 72 hours of life.

Majority of cases admitted were moderate to late preterm [90.5%]. the Mean +/- SD of TSB before and during phototherapy was 18.32 +/- 1.99 mg/dl and 14.16 +/- 2.26 mg/dl. The Mean +/- SD of TcB before and during phototherapy was 19.52 +/- 1.98 mg/dl, 11.05 +/- 2.13 mg/dl. Mean differences [TcB-TSB] before and during phototherapy were 1.2mg/dl, -3.11 mg/dl respectively.

Simultaneously correlation coefficient between TSB & TcB before and during the correlation coefficients 0.97, 0.95 respectively. During phototherapy correlation was slightly poor[r=0.95] as compared to before [r=0.97, p<0.0001]. In our study TcB overestimated TSB before phototherapy and vice versa underestimated during phototherapy.

Figure 2: Scatter plot depicting correlation between TSB and TcB [Before phototherapy]

The correlation coefficient between TSB and TcB before phototherapy was 0.97 [95% CI-0.7704 to 0.8949] and p value was <0.0001, therefore the correlation was found to be statistically significant.

Figure 3: Scatter plot depicting correlation between TSB and TcB [During 24 hrs]

It shows that there is a linear positive correlation [$r=0.95$] during phototherapy in preterm neonates between TcB and TSB. Overall mean \pm SD TcB and TSB over sternum during phototherapy was 11.05 ± 2.13 mg/dl and 14.16 ± 2.26 mg/dl respectively. The correlation coefficient between TSB and TcB during phototherapy was 0.95 and p value < 0.0001 .

Discussion

Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia is the most common cause of readmission to hospital in the new born period. Pre-discharge bilirubin estimation for the prediction of subsequent hyperbilirubinemia is one of the preferred interventions to decrease future complications. Majority of cases admitted were moderate to late preterm [90.5%] therefore mean gestational age in our study was 34.9 weeks. Our study has 9.47% very low birth weight neonate. Extreme low birth weight (< 1000 grams) neonates were not included in our study. In a study by Christian V. Hulzebos *et al* [12] mean age was 29.4 weeks as it included preterm < 32 weeks. In Rakitma *et al* [11] mean gestational age was 37.58 weeks as study included both preterm and term neonates.

The Mean \pm SD of TSB before and during phototherapy was 18.32 ± 1.99 mg/dl, 14.16 ± 2.26 mg/dl respectively. The Mean \pm SD of TcB before, during phototherapy were 19.52 ± 1.98 mg/dl, 11.05 ± 2.13 mg/dl respectively. Mean differences [TCB-TSB] before, during and after

phototherapy were 1.2mg/dl, -3.11 mg/dl. Simultaneously correlation coefficient between TSB & TcB before, during and after the correlation coefficients was 0.97, 0.95. During phototherapy correlation was slightly poor [$r=0.95$] as compared to before [$r=0.97, p < 0.0001$].

In Raktima *et al* [11] similar findings as correlation coefficient decreases during phototherapy [$r=0.3959$] over shielded sternum. Gaurav Nagar *et al* [5] stated that there is very poor correlation between TSB and TcB during phototherapy therefore cannot be used during phototherapy. On the other hand, Amruta Pendse *et al.* [3] reported that, TcB estimation at sternum correlated significantly with TSB prior to initiation of phototherapy [$r=0.903, P < 0.001$] and after phototherapy over the patched sternal area [$r=0.918, P < 0.001$]. In our study transcutaneous bilirubin overestimated before phototherapy [TCB-TSB=1.2mg/dl] but during phototherapy vice versa as mean differences [TCB-TSB] are -3.11mg/dl.

U. Costa-Posad *et al* [33] also stated that TCB and TSB had better correlates during phototherapy in preterm neonate. Before phototherapy TcB overestimated in majority of study population but during phototherapy, TSB overestimated predominantly. Raktima *et al* [11] find the overall tendency of TcB overestimate after cessation of phototherapy but in Zecca *et al* [16] TCB overestimate after initiation of phototherapy.

Christian V. Hulzebos *et al* [12] also had similar findings as the relationship between transcutaneous and total serum bilirubin in preterm infants with and without phototherapy. Study suggestive of the overall correlation between TSB and TcB before, during was similar and statistically significant [$P < 0.01$]. Mean difference between TSB and TcB was significantly lower [$P < 0.05$] before phototherapy than during phototherapy.

Table 1: Comparison of Different Studies Explaining Correlation Between TSB and TcB in Preterm Neonates

S. N.	Name of study	Age group	Sample size	Site	Correlation before PT	Correlation during PT	Correlation after PT
1.	Amruta Pendse <i>et al</i>	28-37 weeks	30	Sternum	No	Yes	No
2.	Lucia Stillova <i>et al</i>	32-34 weeks	44	Forehead, sternum, abdomen	No	Yes	Yes
3.	Gaurav Nagar <i>et al</i>	28-35 weeks	90	Forehead, sternum	Yes	Yes	Yes
4.	Christian. Hulzebos <i>et al</i>	28-35 weeks	109	Hip bone	Yes	Yes	Yes
5.	Jana Grabenhenrich. <i>et al</i>	Both term & Preterm	86	Sternum	Yes	Yes	Yes
6.	Nandjunswamy <i>et al</i>	Preterm	70	Forehead	Yes	Yes	Yes
7.	Raktima Chakrabarti <i>et al</i>	>35 weeks to term	100	Forehead, Sternum	Yes	Yes	Yes
8.	U. Costa-Posada <i>et al</i>	Both term & preterm		Sternum	Yes	Yes	No
9.	Our study	28 weeks to <37 weeks	190	Sternum	Yes	Yes	Yes

Conclusion

In the present study we found that transcutaneous bilirubinometry levels measured on the covered sternal site showed a strong correlation and good agreement with total serum bilirubin levels in preterm infants before, during, and after Phototherapy. It gives fair idea for early

identification risk factors and treatment. Transcutaneous bilirubinometry has the potential to reduce the number of blood samplings, thus reducing neonatal pain and discomfort, parental distress and medical care cost as readings are immediate, and

they can indicate the need for total serum bilirubin testing.

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